
Research

Analysing the Influence of Financial Inclusion on Economic Growth in Uganda

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Abstract: Financial inclusion is essential for fostering stability and economic prosperity, especially in emerging nations like Uganda. In recent years, Uganda has made great progress toward financial inclusion with several initiatives targeted at expanding access to financial services, such as microfinance and mobile banking. International settlements in Uganda have benefited from greater financial inclusion. It has facilitated cross-border trade and investment by providing individuals and businesses with the means to access and transfer funds internationally. This has bolstered the country's economic development and improved its participation in global trade and remittance flows.

This study investigates the impact of financial inclusion on economic growth in Uganda. Utilizing a primary data collection method through structured surveys conducted across diverse demographic segments, the research explores the nuanced relationship between financial inclusion and economic growth. Surprisingly, the findings reveal a positive correlation between increased financial inclusion and economic growth. However, an intriguing aspect emerges as the study identifies a potential negative influence of certain financial services on overall economic development. These results underscore the importance of tailored financial policies to harness the positive aspects of inclusion while mitigating potential drawbacks, fostering a more inclusive and sustainable economic growth trajectory in Uganda. At the end of the paper, the study suggests policy revisions, financial literacy programs, and the promotion of fintech to optimize the positive impact of financial inclusion on economic growth in Uganda.

Keywords: Financial Inclusion, Financial Services, Uganda, and Low-Income Savers.

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Introduction

According to developing countries, financial inclusion is ensuring that individuals and companies have access to affordable and useful financial services. Financial inclusion does not suggest that consumers should use all available resources or that service providers should choose not to take on additional risks or expenses to provide their goods and services (Chikalipah 2017).

Financial inclusion aims to integrate financial services into the mainstream financial system to provide "unbanked" people with access to credit, insurance, payments, transfers, and payments. (Barcellos and Zamarro 2021) A household or small business may not be able to use one or more of the services even with unlimited access because of intentional exclusion as well as unfavorable risk-return characteristics. Policy involvement is not necessarily warranted by such results. Policy initiatives should target market imperfections rather than eliminating non-market barriers to obtaining a wide variety of financial services. Credit unions, savings cooperatives, and microfinance organizations have come a long way in the last two decades, but most of the world's impoverished are still unreached by formal financial intermediaries that can securely handle cash and act as a link between net savers and net borrowers.

According to (Makanjee 2009) Six of Uganda's 13 Maya Declaration targets are still unfinished, while seven have already been accomplished. Uganda's focus areas include financial inclusion data, e-money, international standards, agent banking, Consumer protection, financial identity, credit information systems, financial inclusion statistics, consumer empowerment and market behavior, financial literacy and education, microcredit and micro-savings, and financial integrity.

On October 26, 2017, Uganda conducted a ceremony to officially introduce its National Financial Inclusion Strategy (2017–2022). According to (Eton, Gilbert, et al. 2019), Ugandans have access to and use a wide range of quality and affordable financial services which help ensure their financial security and to also improve the welfare of Ugandan citizens, and contribute to socio-economic development". By 2022, the NFIS wants to lower the percentage of financial exclusion from 15% to 5%.

Over the past ten years, the economy of Uganda has expanded significantly, but the high rates of financial exclusion in rural places limit future employment opportunities (Koku 2015). Particularly in rural areas and among the poorer sectors of the population, the high cost of providing financial services is one of the factors contributing to the low levels of formal financial inclusion. Financial service providers usually make less money servicing poorer communities because disadvantaged households have fewer investment options and smaller transaction amounts. This frequently indicates that banks and micro-finance organizations lack the motivation, knowledge, and occasionally even the capacity to reduce the perceived risks associated with conducting business outside of urban markets or with low-income clients.

More savings accounts exist than individuals in the entire world, according to the Consultative Group to Assist the Poor (CGAP). However, formal savings accounts and other financial services are inaccessible to 2.5 billion adults globally (Reille, Glisovic-Mezieres, et al. 2009). As a policy aim, financial inclusion is now agreed upon in a long-running conversation about how finance helps economic development and poverty alleviation. It provides significant insights into the beneficial impact that financial services have on the (economic) lives of the impoverished and maps out the development of financial sector policies in developing nations over the previous few decades.

Background of the Study

According to (Okello Candiya Bongomin, Ntayi, et al. 2016) Financial literacy, consumer protection against financial fraud, financial innovation, and financial data and assessment served as the foundation for Uganda's inaugural financial inclusion project. Financial inclusion in emerging markets was 63 percent in 2017. Since 2014, Sub-Saharan Africa has seen a four percentage point increase in the percentage of people with bank accounts and a nine percentage point increase in those with mobile accounts. (Assuming, Osei-Agyei et al. 2019) Uganda's formal financial inclusion has nearly doubled from 28% in 2009 to 58% in 2018. Increased financial inclusion was made possible in large part by the use of mobile money services, which were adopted by adults (56% of whom either had an account or used mobile money services). Mobile money and other digital financial services have played a significant role in this.

The most recent financial crisis has demonstrated the destructive systemic effects that financial innovation may have. A worldwide concentrated effort to revise and tighten financial laws has been made as a response by international standard-setters and national regulators. At a time when stricter regulations are being designed, it is imperative to avoid

a reaction against financial inclusion (Claessens and Rojas-Suarez 2016). Additionally, with the use of well-known prudential measures and improved customer protection, risks that are common at the institutional level can be controlled.

Financial inclusion may have costs, but these are balanced by large dynamic benefits that, as a result of a deeper and more diversified financial system, improve financial stability over time. We outline the current situation of financial inclusion around the world in the pages that follow. We also look at some current developments in financial inclusion and the best regulatory frameworks to support it. Thus, we propose that financial inclusion-fighting innovations might benefit financial systems as opposed to harming them.

Institutional hazards associated with financial inclusion exist, but they are not very systemic (Beck, Demirgüç-Kunt et al. 2009). Research reveals that low-income borrowers and savers usually handle money sensibly during financial crises, paying back loans and keeping safe deposit boxes. A significant percentage of weak clients with small balances and few transactions characterize institutional risk profiles at the low end of the financial market. There is little risk of financial instability from inclusive policies, even though this profile may raise concerns about possible harm to the central bank's reputation and consumer protection.

According to recent research, having access to financial services, particularly through digital financial services, has the potential to enhance saving habits, cut the cost of money transfers, control risks, and raise income-generating capacity. In general, Uganda's efforts to promote financial inclusion have been in line with the country's financial sector reforms, which have strengthened market competition and improved the efficiency of financial service delivery by increasing prudential regulation and supervision. (Galbis 1995).

An independent non-profit organization, Financial Sector Deepening Uganda (FSDU) is working to increase Ugandans' access to financial services (Nannyonjo 2002). With an emphasis on low-income earners (especially women) and Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises, FSD Uganda aims to create a more equitable financial system (Eton, Fabian et al. 2018). They undertake research and encourage and help develop legislation, laws, and regulations that influence Uganda's financial sector. They also foster innovation. FSD Uganda collaborates with stakeholders in the public and private sectors to improve the lives of people with low incomes in a sustainable way by lowering their vulnerability to shocks, raising their incomes, and creating employment opportunities.

To let MTN Uganda, the nation's first mobile money service provider, collaborate with Stanbic Bank(U) Limited to provide financial services utilizing mobile money, the Bank of Uganda issued a letter of no objection in 2009. By the first Maya Declaration, the Bank of Uganda pledged to promote financial inclusion when it joined the Alliance for Financial Inclusion in 2011 (Soederberg 2013). The ecosystem is composed of the Bank of Uganda, commercial banks, non-bank financial institutions, mobile network providers, third-party operators, and technology vendors. Interoperability is still limited, though, and temporary solutions include bilateral contracts between different MMSPs and their associated financial institution partners. In March 2009, MTN Uganda and Stanbic Bank joined up to create mobile money services in Uganda. Since then, mobile payments have significantly increased financial inclusion in Uganda thanks to their competitive market and remarkable growth.

In conclusion, Mobile money service providers, such as MTN Uganda, Airtel Uganda, UTL, Africell, M-Cash, Ezee Money, and Micro pay, are principally responsible for dominating the Ugandan market for digital financial services (Hinman and Matovu 2010). The BoU's main regulatory priority has been to make sure that customer funds are secure while purchasing electronic value from mobile money agents with cash. Currently, MNOs and other MMSPs that utilize the MNOs' networks in collaboration with regulated financial institutions offer mobile money services. With their partner deposit-taking supervised financial institution, the MMSPs are expected to maintain escrow accounts with an amount equal to all of the e-value they have distributed to their clients and agents.

Literature Review: Strategic View

According to (Joshi 2014), financial inclusion is the equitable and transparent process wherein prominent institutional players ensure that marginalized groups, like lower-income and weaker sectors, have inexpensive accessibility to essential products and services. Financial services are offered by numerous providers in a stable and competitive market, catering to the needs of all consumers. According to the Central Bank of Brazil's (2010) Annual Report on Financial Inclusion, financial inclusion is the process of efficiently obtaining and utilizing financial services that are suitable for their requirements and enhance their standard of living. The United Nations Advisory Group on Financial Inclusion was founded by the United Nations in 2006. This body provides advice to the UN and its member states on matters about the global progress of the financial inclusion agenda.

Asian nations like India and Indonesia have a long history of stressing financial access (Cooperation 2018). These policy objectives have proven successful locally, according to (Beck and De la Torre 2006): 25% of households making less than \$2 per day currently have access to formal or semi-formal financial services, compared to (40–50)% of the total population. Since 2006, the successful turnaround of Mongolia's national bank has resulted in a growth of more than 1.4 million deposit accounts; currently, 62% of households have a deposit account (Murakami 2022).

In the Philippines Since 2002, the number of customers served by mobile phone banking has increased to 4 million (Habaradas and Umali 2013). India: As the micro-finance industry recruited 9.9 million customers, the percentage of the poor who had access to credit increased from 7 percent in 2004 to 20.5 percent in 2009. Bangladesh: Since 2006, 4-6 million additional microcredit customers have been recruited. Approximately 55% of impoverished households now have access to financial services, which significantly improves one's capacity for saving. (Mader 2013).

The lack of access to deposits is another issue facing the destitute in India: Even though there are now over 28 million "no frills" accounts, research suggests that a large portion of these accounts are dormant. Public banks or nonbank institutions like nongovernmental organizations typically provide services to the impoverished, except private sector banks, which are mostly found in Asia. These public banks and nonbank institutions including, for example, Post Savings Bank in Pakistan, had 3.6 million accounts as of 2006. India: As of March 2007, post offices had 60.8 million savings accounts. The Rural Development Board of Bangladesh had 4.7 million active borrowers as of 2007. In addition, despite significant advancements in Bangladesh and India, an estimated 535 million individuals in these two nations still lack access to financial services.

In Vietnam, according to the (Shastri 2009) Bank for Social Policy had 6.79 million active borrowers in 2008 and the Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development had 10 million farmer clients in 2007. In addition, there have been 2.1 million more microfinance customers added since 2006. According to (Kavaney 2007), 36 million accounts were in Thailand's Government Savings Bank as of 2006. In 2006, 72 percent of households in Sri Lanka used state banks. However, the bulk of institutions depend on subsidies, and the quality of services is poor even with this outreach.

According to (Akileng, Lawino et al. 2018), The UNDP (2012) emphasizes the need for financial inclusion for all market sectors, emphasizing that the impoverished who are frequently disregarded, additionally require access to a range of banking services, including chances to earn, protection of their hard-earned money, and credit to help them in preserving the barest basic standards of nutrition throughout the year, using risk-reduction services like insurance, and sending their money to loved ones who could be traveling. Center for Financial Inclusion (2015) elaborates that financial inclusion is a state in which everyone has access to financial services, which include microloans, savings accounts, insurance, electronic payments, and remittances. These examples of financial services are provided above. But for households to comprehend and take advantage of these financial services, there is a need for financial literacy which can be improved through offering financial education.

In Uganda, Central banks, like the Bank of Uganda, engage in international settlements and transactions with other central banks through the BIS or other channels to maintain foreign exchange reserves and guarantee financial system stability.

According to (Fisk 1930), The Bank for International Settlements (BIS) is a global financial organization that mainly assists central banks and works to advance monetary and financial stability around the globe. Financial knowledge and literacy, consumer protection, and empowerment are essential for the use of online financial services in Uganda.

The National Strategy for Financial Literacy (2019–2024) has been finalized by the BoU in collaboration with other stakeholders, and it is anticipated that concerns with financial literacy and awareness will be addressed through the implementation of the strategy (Khokhar and Kaur 2022). The World Bank created the Global Findex database in 2011 with assistance from the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (Demirgüç-Kunt, Klapper et al. 2020). This database is the most comprehensive source of data on adult risk management, loan repayment, savings, and bill payment practices. Based on poll data collected in collaboration with Gallup, Inc., the Global Findex database contains information on over 140 economies worldwide.

Uganda is falling short of other nations where surveys have been carried out by researchers in terms of the percentage of persons who utilize financial services (Gershenberg 1972). Financial Service Providers, including banks, have no incentive to serve rural areas due to the high expense of doing so. This indicates that 24% of Ugandans living in urban areas access bank services, whereas only 7% of those living in rural areas access bank services. Uganda will need to come up with creative ways to reach rural consumers if it is to boost the banking industry. Examples of such innovations include mobile banking and agent banking, which were adopted in Uganda lately after being established in Tanzania in 2013 (Demirgüç-Kunt and Klapper 2012). These figures indicate that there is a good opportunity to grow banking through mobile services.

Financial inclusion and economic growth have been associated in many nations now view financial inclusion as a way to attain greater comprehensive development. Different countries around the globe have acknowledged the significance of financial inclusion. Numerous accomplishments have been made since its founding, such as raising public awareness of the need for financial inclusion and supporting governments in developing regulatory frameworks that enable the development of financial services for the underprivileged, assembling and sharing best practices, working with the corporate sector to use skills and technology to further enhance financial inclusion, and supporting research that will spark new initiatives.

Research Methodology

This paper analyses descriptive research where the researcher analyzed primary data collected because it spans both quantitative and qualitative methods to describe, which gives the researcher the flexibility to explain occurrences in more or less detail as needed, thus allowing them to employ quantitative statistics to meaningfully organize their data. This research was carried out with the help of a mixed-methods approach recommended by (Silverio, Sheen, et al. 2022) making use of qualitative and quantitative data. The sample survey's results can be categorized by geographic characteristics (rural or urban) regions, as well as, demographic characteristics including; sex, socioeconomic status, and, primary financial services utilized. For example (bank or mobile money). The data collected was tabulated using an Excel sheet and then analyzed using a statistical package called Stata. According to (Ball 1965) Data analysis is inspecting and sorting data to obtain helpful information that the reader can interpret or understand. The descriptive analysis, which includes means and percentages, was used to analyze the findings of the study. Regression, a component of inferential analysis, was utilized to determine the relationship between the obtained data's independent and dependent variables.

Data analysis and results

Descriptive Analysis

The report's part on Ugandan adults' salient key characteristics and abilities that were taken into account when designing and promoting their services is presented here. Gender, age, educational attainment, financial inclusion, and

financial services are among the important demographic traits of the respondents that were analyzed. Additional elements that were examined were social capital, digital connectivity, sources of income, and financial competence.

Table 1. SUMMARY STATISTICS OF THE PRIMARY DATA

Variable name	Frequency	percent
Sex		
Male	80	40
Female	120	60
Total	200	100
Region		
Urban	172	86
Rural	28	14
Total	200	100
Level of education		
High school	30	15
Diploma	61	30.5
Degree	49	24.5
Master’s degree	55	27.5
PhD	5	2.5
Total	200	100
financial services		
saving	93	46.5
credit	43	21.5
insurance	28	14
investment	36	18
Total	200	100

Data source: Primary data.

The population's baseline size and age with sex distribution is crucial, and they are occasionally reinforced by additional factors for example region (urban vs. rural), financial services used in receiving, transferring, and saving money, for example, mobile money, banks, and other internet-based platforms. From the output Table 1, the findings indicate that 14% of respondents in Uganda live in rural areas, while 86% of respondents live in urban areas. This demonstrates a significant urbanization trend, where a majority of adults are concentrated in cities and towns due to looking for greener pastures in urban areas. In the study, a significant majority of the respondents were female. This accounted for a proportion of 60% as compared to 40% of the respondents who were males. The difference between the two percentages for the sexes was 20% implying that the final results reflected more views from the female respondents than the males.

The analysis of the geographical distribution of the adult population in terms of financial inclusion reveals disparities in financial services availability between urban areas and rural areas. saving ranking high with 46.5%, which implies that the biggest population saves rather than investing (18%) thus discouraging economic growth. This shows the need for policymakers and financial institutions to bridge these gaps by tailoring services to the specific requirements of each setting and promoting financial literacy and inclusion for all.

Summary Statistics Of The Study Variables

Regardless of an individual's or business's size or personal net worth, financial inclusion refers to initiatives taken to make

saving, investment, credits, and financial education available and cheap to different parties. (Demirgüç-Kunt and Klapper 2012). It explains adult respondents who have used financial inclusion to settle transactions in urban areas across those who have used financial inclusion in rural areas, any of those in the specification of with business and without.

Table 2:SUMMARY STATISTICS OF THE STUDY VARIABLES

Variable	N	MEAN	Std. deviation	minimum	maximum
Access microcredit	200	0.22	0.415	0	1
Access banking services	200	0.29	0.455	0	1
Financial education	200	0.49	0.501	0	1

Data source: Primary Data

Table 2 summarizes the responses of respondents who participated in financial inclusion to make financial settlements. The result indicates that out of the 200 respondents who were involved in the study, on average (0.22) of the respondents can access microcredits in making transactions. for instance, Small and independent firms find it more difficult to obtain loans, insurance, and investments that will support business growth since they lack access to traditional financial resources from larger organizations, and the standard deviation is 0.415. The minimum (0) was for those who didn't have access to microcredits and the maximum (1) was for those who had access to microcredits.

The result indicates that out of the 200 respondents who were involved in the study, on average (0.29) of the respondents accessed banking services in both rural and urban areas when making transactions. Ensuring that banking services are both accessible and affordable is crucial to enabling underbanked and unbanked individuals to engage with the formal financial system. Local financial inclusion is aided by the availability of low-cost transaction accounts and basic savings accounts. This upholds financial security and encourages saving money. For example, (easy banking, Digital payments, mobile banking, and saving) and the standard deviation is 0.455. The minimum (0) was for those who didn't have access to bank services and the maximum (1) was for those who had access to bank services for financial settlements.

The result indicates that out of the 200 respondents who were involved in the study, on average (0.49), the respondents had financial education in making transactions, for example, easy banking and it had a standard deviation (0.501). The minimum (0) was for those who never had financial education and the maximum (1) was for those who had financial education for financial settlements, for example, investments, insurance, credits, and savings. This implies that the biggest population in Uganda has a financial education system especially those in urban areas. This had generally increased during the pandemic when services were digitalized., therefore access to different financial services is very convenient and safer.

Correlation Analysis

Correlation was used to find out the relationship between financial inclusion and other variables like region, gender, and financial services. Pearson correlation(Solutions 2019) was used to test the interrelationship between financial services (saving, credit, insurance, investment) and financial inclusion(access microcredits, access banking services, financial education).

Table 3: The Correlation Analysis Between Financial Inclusion, Education Level And Financial Services.

Key								
	rho							
	Sig. level							
	financial inclusion	education level	saving	credit	investment	region	gender	
financial inclusion	1.0000							
education level	0.2636	1.0000						
	0.0002							
saving	-0.1160	-0.5342	1.0000					
	0.1019	0.0000						
credit	0.1230	0.2655	-0.4879	1.0000				
	0.0828	0.0001	0.0000					
investment	0.0815	0.4227	-0.4368	-0.2452	1.0000			
	0.2510	0.0000	0.0000	0.0005				
region	-0.2082	-0.0078	-0.1450	0.0344	0.1110	1.0000		
	0.0031	0.9132	0.0405	0.6289	0.1176			
gender	-0.0974	-0.2599	0.2292	-0.0696	-0.0956	-0.0235	1.0000	
	0.1702	0.0002	0.0011	0.3277	0.1779	0.7408		

Source: Primary Data

From the above table 3, the correlation coefficient between financial inclusion and education level is (0.264), which indicates a positive relationship between the two variables, thus an increase in the education level leads to an increase in access to banking services, microfinance credits, and financial education because people will have more knowledge of what services are being provided and since its p-value(0.002) then the relationship between the two variables is statistically significant.

The correlation coefficient between financial inclusion and region is (-0.208), which indicates a negative relationship between the two variables, implying that a change in the region by a respondent led to a decrease in the level of financial inclusion. This is seen especially in rural areas where the accessibility of banks, microcredits, and financial education is limited which makes it difficult to save or access loans and since its p-value(0.003), then the relationship between the two variables is statistically significant.

The correlation coefficient between the level of education and saving is (-0.534), which indicates a negative relationship between the two variables, implying that an addition of one year of education led to a decrease in savings of a respondent. This is because, as one is in school, they may have part-time or no jobs that would provide enough income for them to save, and since its p-value(0.0000), then the relationship between the two variables is statistically significant.

The correlation coefficient between level of education and credit is (0.266), which indicates a positive relationship between the two variables, implying that an increase in the years of education by one led to an increase in the number of loans acquired by the respondent since they have different ideas and knowledge (the discounts put up by the banks and microcredits) on how to make investments(0.423) and increase profits, and since its p-value(0.0001), then the relationship between the two variables is statistically significant.

The correlation coefficient between saving and credit is negative, which indicates a negative correlation, implying that an increase in the level of savings led to a decrease in the loans acquired and the investments made by the respondent, thus reducing the country's GDP because there is no production of goods and services, this, in the long run, leads to unemployment. and since the p-values are (0.0000), then the relationship between the two variables is statistically significant.

Overall, data suggests that digital bank services are more widely used by the adult population in Uganda compared to

traditional bank services. It's interesting to note that a significant percentage of adults have used mobile money, while a smaller percentage have used traditional banks. Additionally, a notable proportion of adults in business rely on both mobile money and traditional bank services for their activities. Even though carriers have switched from the SIM tool Kit to the Unstructured Supplementary Service Data model, a subscriber can only use the mobile money service of the SIM card used in the present model. The maker of the SIM card, (Almazán and Sitbon 2014) predicts that as the use of smartphones increases, this situation will change. This is because it is believed that by disabling the SIM card's connection to the mobile money service, smartphones can reduce entry barriers, allowing a wider range of businesses to take advantage of the mobile money market and upend established business models. Improved user experiences can also be obtained through web- or app-based interfaces. These findings and forecasts suggest that the opportunities for innovation and invention of mobile money are still vivid and viable.

Regression Analysis .Multiple linear regression analysis

According to(Uyanık and Güler 2013), Multiple linear regression is a statistical technique that is used to predict the outcome of two or more independent variables. (while holding all others constant). I ran a regression model using financial inclusion as the (independent value) and region, gender, age, level of education, and financial services as the dependent variables keeping other factors constant.

Table 4: Regression Analysis Results

Dependent variable	Financial inclusion (Y)			
Independent variables	coefficients	Std. deviation	t	sig
Constant	2.472	0.42	5.89	0.00
Region	-0.519	0.158	-3.28	0.001
Age	0.003	0.028	0.12	0.905
Gender	-0.067	0.115	-0.58	0.561
Education level	0.159	0.139	1.15	0.253
Financial services	-0.006	0.056	-0.10	0.917
Observations= 200	Prob> f=0.0000	R-squared=0.114	Adjusted R ² =0.091	F (5, 194)=4.97

Data source: Primary Data

From Table 4, R-squared is low at 0.114, suggesting that region, age, gender, education level, and financial services explain only a small proportion(11.4%) of the variations in financial inclusion. Additionally, a low R-squared value and relatively high p-values for some variables suggest that the model may not be a strong predictor for the dependent variable. Further analysis of additional variables may be needed to improve the model's performance. F (5, 194), the F-statistic value tests the overall significance of the regression model. The F-statistic coefficient is 4.97, which is relatively low.

From the above analysis in Table Figure 4.3.1, our regression model is:

Financial inclusion= 2.472 -0.520region +0.003age -0.067gender + 0.159education level -0.006 financial services +u.

Financial services

Based on the provided statistics from Table 4 above, the regression model indicates a negative relationship between financial services (-0.006) for instance, (saving, investment, offering of credits and insurance) and financial inclusion(access micro-credits, access banking services, financial education), implying that as the level of financial services rises the level of financial inclusion tends to reduce. An increase in financial services has the potential to enhance financial inclusion, especially if efforts are made to ensure accessibility, affordability, and tailored solutions for underserved populations. However, it depends on the implementation

and inclusivity of these services. The analysis results of the regression model between the two variables (financial services and financial inclusion) indicate a hindrance in economic growth and exacerbate inequality. The limited access to banking, credit, and insurance can impede individuals and businesses from participating fully in the economy.

Governments and organizations often strive to address these issues through policies that promote inclusive financial systems, aiming to uplift marginalized communities and promote overall economic stability. In summary, In Uganda among the most promising mobile applications are mobile banking services. The delivery of financial services on a mobile platform is the most fundamental definition of mobile money. Mobile banking comprises a variety of services, including banking, for instance, account balance queries, finance; insurance products, and payments; and peer-to-peer transfers. In other words, ensuring that (low-banked and unbanked) people can engage with the formal financial system is ensured by providing them with accessible and reasonably priced banking services(Beck, Demirgüç-Kunt, et al. 2009). Facilitating basic savings accounts and inexpensive transaction accounts which allows grassroots financial inclusion, thus encouraging saving and upholding financial security (both literally and mentally).

Education level and financial inclusion

Based on the provided statistics in Table 5, the regression model indicates that there is a high positive relationship between education level, for example, high school, diploma, bachelor's, master's degree, Ph.D., and financial inclusion, implying that as the level of education increases, financial inclusion tends to increase as well.

Table 5: EFFECT OF FINANCIAL INCLUSION ON EDUCATION

Dependent variable	Financial inclusion (Y)			
Independent variables	coefficients	Std. deviation	t	sig
constant	1.789	0.167	10.72	0.000
Region	-0.248	0.071	-3.47	0.001
Age	0.001	0.012	0.08	0.934
Education level	0.021	0.625	0.34	0.736
Financial education	1.394	0.510	27.32	0.000
Observations= 200				
	Prob> f=0.0000	R-squared=0.816	Adjusted R²=0.812	F(4,195)=216.23

Data source: Primary Data

In Uganda, more educated people tend to have more access to microcredits and banking services due to the knowledge they have about them. Education level (0.021) can significantly influence financial inclusion. Higher levels of education often correlate with better financial literacy, which in turn increases the effective use of financial services. On the other hand, educational programs and initiatives like financial education (1.394) played a crucial role in promoting financial inclusion by empowering individuals to make informed decisions on finances and engage with a broader range of financial services.

Financial inclusion and education level are interconnected in several ways. Higher education levels often correlate with better financial inclusion due to increased knowledge, skills, and access to opportunities. Individuals with higher education, such as a master's or PhD, tend to have better financial literacy, making them more adept at managing their finances, investing, and

participating in the formal financial system. This education level can lead to increased income, financial stability, and a higher likelihood of utilizing various financial services.

On the other hand, apart from the education level, age(0.018) and financial inclusion had a positive relationship. Younger people may find it difficult to obtain standard financial services because of their short credit history, while older populations might encounter barriers related to technology adoption. Tailoring financial products to the needs of different age groups and promoting digital literacy can contribute to more inclusive financial systems.

Figure 1: A BAR GRAPH REPRESENTS FINANCIAL INCLUSION AND EDUCATION LEVEL.

Data source: Primary Data

In Figure 1, I constructed a bar graph that indicates the means of different education levels in relation to financial inclusion of how the respondents can easily access microcredits, access banking services, and access financial education in Uganda.

The bar graph above explains the level of financial inclusion in relation to the education level in Uganda. Respondents with the highest level of education(PHD) have financial literacy on how to access microcredit, for instance, the requirement one needs to acquire loans, and open up savings accounts through accessing bank services when making transactions, so its financial inclusion is the highest compared to other respondents of different levels.

Conversely, those with lower education levels, like high school or diploma holders, may face challenges in understanding complex financial concepts and navigating financial systems. This can result in limited access to banking services, credit, and investment opportunities, potentially leading to financial exclusion. Promoting financial education at all levels can enhance financial inclusion by empowering people to have the information and abilities necessary to make wise financial decisions, irrespective of the formal education level. The government of Uganda has set up different credit schemes to support youths by offering long-term loans that can help them push up or start up different businesses to reduce unemployment rates and high crime rates in the country. These incentives have been put up for youth of all ages (18-35), thus reducing income inequalities and, as well, increasing Uganda’s GDP.

Impact of financial inclusion on economic growth.

Individuals with and without businesses have access to financial services, thus in a better position to engage in international trade and investment. This increased participation can contribute to the growth of global economic activities. This can be through financial services like savings, credit, insurance, and investment.

Financial inclusion leads to more efficient and cost-effective international settlements. Accessibility of digital financial

services, for example, can streamline transactions, reduce paperwork, and lower transaction costs, benefiting both individuals and businesses involved in international trade. The provision of a broader base of participants with access to financial tools can help mitigate risks in international settlements. Diverse financial services, such as insurance and hedging instruments, can assist in managing risks associated with currency fluctuations, market uncertainties, and other factors affecting international transactions.

A financially inclusive global economy may be more stable and resilient. When a large portion of the population has access to financial resources, there's a potential for more balanced economic development, reducing vulnerability to economic shocks. Financial inclusion often involves the integration of innovative technologies. These technologies can enhance the efficiency of service deliveries and the production of high-quality goods, such as blockchain for secure and transparent transactions.

In Uganda, financial inclusion has established room to address economic disparities and promote sustainable development. This, in turn, can positively influence international relationships and collaborations. In summary, the impact of financial inclusion on international settlements is multifaceted, ranging from increased efficiency and reduced costs to greater stability and resilience in the global financial system. Moreover, it contributes to broader socio-economic development, fostering a more interconnected and inclusive global economy.

Conclusion

In Uganda, financial inclusion and financial services have a symbiotic relationship, where the growth of one significantly influences the other in a negative direction. While an increase in financial services is generally associated with positive outcomes for financial inclusion, in Uganda different aspects lead to negative aspects arising. (Kim, Zoo, et al. 2018) Some causes of negative financial inclusion despite an increase in financial services, include a lack of awareness and education. If the population doesn't have sufficient knowledge or awareness about the available financial services, they may not utilize them effectively, leading to negative financial inclusion as well as increased reliance on digital financial services may exclude individuals with limited access to technology, exacerbating existing socioeconomic disparities. Some financial services come with fees or charges that are prohibitive for certain segments of the population, making them less accessible to those who need them the most.

Nonetheless, (Jagtap 2016) Uganda faces several challenges in achieving full financial inclusion, including rural infrastructure limitations, low financial literacy, and regulatory obstacles. These challenges need to be addressed to ensure that the benefits of financial inclusion are widespread and equitable. Doing so will further stimulate economic growth, reduce poverty, and enhance Uganda's global economic integration. Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach that includes financial education, addressing infrastructure gaps, creating user-friendly services, and ensuring that regulations support rather than hinder financial inclusion efforts. The efforts to enhance financial inclusion have contributed positively to the country's economic growth in terms of GDP. This is evident through recent research on increased cross-border trade, improved access to international remittances, and enhanced participation in global financial systems.

The analysis makes it abundantly evident to those in the business how financial inclusion affects Uganda's economic expansion. The study has shown that to increase financial inclusion, greater efforts should be made in rural areas and more bank branches should be opened there with priority. Banks and insurance companies, among other market participants, should thus come up with strategies to encourage these difficulties.

The study has significantly advanced our understanding of the relationships between the several elements influencing financial inclusion, according to academics. It has also given researchers a better understanding of potential topics to investigate in the future. The study has shed light on the value of financial inclusion for the general people. Additionally, the investigation has revealed the variables that control the degree of financial inclusion and how these variables can be strengthened.

In light of this, continued collaboration between government institutions, financial service providers, and international organizations is essential. A concerted effort to improve financial education, expand the reach of financial services, and streamline regulations will not only strengthen financial inclusion but also propel Uganda toward a more

prosperous and economically integrated future on the global stage.

Recommendations

Although financial inclusion originated in the banking sectors of wealthy nations, the global economic crisis will likely refocus future financial inclusion efforts. The crisis has prompted a thorough reassessment of the government's involvement in the financial sector, which has greatly accelerated the pace of regulatory reform.

Policymakers ought to leverage the ongoing reform movement to strengthen financial inclusion programs that bolster economic resilience. Thoroughly analyzing the risks associated with subpar transactions is essential to boosting financial inclusion after the crisis. Without this kind of analysis, the heightened sense of danger might result in a general prohibition on innovation.

Legislators should draft laws addressing financial inclusion with the help of successful ideas developed by their peers that safely achieve its benefits. Supported by the Alliance for Financial Inclusion, a global network of developing country researchers, peer-to-peer contact among developing countries will aid in the development and dissemination of these concepts, enabling other countries to adjust and expand on successful projects.

Research has demonstrated that financial inclusion also lessens income disparity. A more cohesive society helps avert political unrest and allows crisis management to get full focus. Social safety nets have the potential to enhance financial inclusion when they offer benefits via standard bank accounts within the official financial sector. Government policy has prioritized consumer protection as a result of the subprime crisis, which highlighted the risks associated with reckless lending practices. Financial education programs have been attaining traction lately. Researchers now see a better justification for including financial education in the curricula of high schools and colleges, and they are hoping that the private sector will play a bigger role in this effort.

Financial inclusion initiatives aim to improve accessibility of financial services that will better people's way of living. In terms of cash flow and risk management, this refers to services that guarantee people can pay their regular bills and yet have money left over to cover unforeseen costs both now and in the future. Therefore, the focus of this section of the research is on the financial management techniques used by Ugandan adults to deal with regular expenses, unforeseen expenses, life cycle events, and long-term financial stability. Since research indicates that income is also necessary for improved financial inclusion, the government should tighten its regulations regarding the assistance it provides to the unemployed so they can start enterprises and earn more money.

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